

Formatted examples of choice sets

Choosing Possible Waterfowl Hunting Sites

Consider the two sites in each table below. Each site has different levels of site attributes like driving distance and habitat. ([Click here for a reminder of what these attribute levels mean.](#))

Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 1

<u>Attribute</u>	<u>Site A</u>	<u>Site B</u>
Habitat type	 Dense Vegetation	
Water levels	Managed	Natural
Chance of hunting success	10%	10%
Huntable area	1,000 acres	5,000 acres
Crowding affects shots	Medium	High
Round trip driving time	180 minutes	60 minutes

1. Based on the hunting site attributes in the table above, which site would you hunt at?

I would hunt Site A

I would hunt Site B

I would not go hunting

Choosing Possible Waterfowl Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 5)

Here are two other possible hunting sites. Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 2

<u>Attribute</u>	<u>Site C</u>	<u>Site D</u>
Habitat type	 Sparse Vegetation	
Water levels	Natural	Managed
Chance of hunting success	60%	30%
Huntable area	5,000 acres	5,000 acres
Crowding affects shots	Medium	Medium
Round trip driving time	300 minutes	120 minutes

1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

I would hunt Site C

I would hunt Site D

I would not go hunting